

MODEL OF PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL SUPPORT PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHERS IN THE SYSTEM EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The article describes the features of the model of psychological and pedagogical support of teachers as a means of improving the level of professional formation in the process of training in the system of postgraduate pedagogical education. In its structure there are five units: task, organizational, substantive, procedural, and assessment-effective. Mechanisms of implementation of this psycho-pedagogical support are: implementation of various support functions; the development of key competences of teachers as their professional development; to provide various types of support.*

Keywords: *model, modeling, model structure, model of psycho-pedagogical support mechanisms for the implementation of psycho-pedagogical support; types of support; types of psychological support: fostering, collaborative, consulting, moderation*

INTRODUCTION

To study the most complicated processes in science, modeling is often used as a method of studying objects on similar constructions, building and researching a specific part of social reality. Hence, modeling (from the French. Modele - sample, prototype) - building a model of the object under study.

A model is a system of elements that reproduces certain aspects, relationships, functions of the subject of study (the original). Distinguish between material (subject) and symbolic (diagrams, drawings, formulas) models, as well as layouts or descriptions. The model reproduces only some aspects of the original that are important in this study. Its creation involves elements of counseling, in which, firstly, the study of already known components (details) in a new combination is allowed; secondly, the release of the structure from small details, non-essential features and characteristics; thirdly, the adaptation of some parts to the new content [3].

Material and methods. Modeling as a method has recently been often used in pedagogical research. The modeling process of education is devoted to a number of major scientific research (E.N. Stepanov and others). According to E.N. Stepanov, the main characteristic category for modeling and its main feature (in relation to other methods) is mediation, since the researcher, solving the cognitive task using the modeling method, sets between himself and the studied fragment of social reality an object - the deputy of the original, that is, the model, the study of which allows you to get a new study on the studied social phenomenon [7].

The modeling process consists of several stages (stages). In psychological and pedagogical research, there are different points of view about how many stages should be and how they should be called. M.K. Buslova, for example, indicates several stages in the modeling procedure: 1) statement of the problem; 2) theoretical and experimental training; 3) model creation; 4) model research; 5) transfer of the received information to the studied object; 6) putting forward a

scientific hypothesis based on the knowledge gained and its verification; 7) the inclusion of acquired knowledge in scientific theory [2].

Results and discussion. Studying the design of pedagogical systems in detail, B.C. Bezrukova identifies three stages (steps) in it: modeling, design and construction itself. In this sense, pedagogical modeling is presented as creating a model, developing a general idea of pedagogical systems, processes or situations of the main ways to achieve them [1].

So, the modeling process itself involves:

- model development;
- its adaptation to the real educational process;
- verification of its effectiveness.

The model can be considered successful in cases where it demonstrates a behavior similar to the original, or allows you to detect until now unknown properties of the studied phenomenon. Therefore, traditionally in pedagogy, the emphasis in modeling is on the analysis of the effectiveness of the functioning of an object of study (G. Klaus), in our case, the process of professional formation of a teacher. However, if the technology for reconstructing the existing ideas about the process is proposed and justified, then we can talk about the transforming function of modeling (N.I. Lyapunova). Therefore, we can agree that the use of modeling (creating a model) will help to increase the effectiveness of the process under study in the practice of postgraduate teacher education, as it will make it possible to consciously and pedagogically influence its individual components, make adjustments to the content and forms.

From a pedagogical point of view, the model has a certain structure, which includes the goal, principles, content, methods, forms, means, and focuses on understanding the achieved result, which allows one to determine the same elements for the next round.

When developing the model, we relied on the scientific principles of pedagogical modeling (V.P. Bepalko, V.I. Zagvyazinsky, V.S. Ilyin, V.A. Slastenin, V.A. Shtoff, etc.), andragogical approach to adult education (S.I. Zmeyev, A.I. Kukuev, M. Knowles). From these positions, a structural-dynamic model of psychological and pedagogical support for the professional development of a teacher was designed and its description is given.

The model we presented consists of five blocks: target, organizational, substantive, procedural, and evaluative and effective.

At the basis of the target block of the model of psychological and pedagogical support of the teacher's professional development, we have indicated the following goal: to increase the level of the teacher's professional development in the process of his education in the system of postgraduate teacher education.

The model of psychological and pedagogical support is aimed at solving the following problems:

1. Creation of a complex of conditions ensuring an increase in the level of professional formation of a teacher in the system of postgraduate teacher education
2. Improving the teacher's core competencies as indicators of increasing the level of teacher professional development.
3. Improving the professional development of teachers through the provision of various types of support.

The principles in building a model of psychological and pedagogical support for the professional development of a teacher are:

- andragogical, which implements the general requirements for the organization of adult education: self-study, joint activities, relying on the experience of students, individualization, context, electivity, the development of educational needs, etc.;

- humanization, providing for the reassessment of all components of the educational process, when the professional and personal development of the teacher becomes the leader;

- Facilitation, involving the creation of favorable conditions for the educational activities of teachers: stimulation, activation of their professional development; designed to facilitate the process of overcoming obstacles, difficulties and problems that impede professional success;

- cooperation, giving the opportunity to transfer knowledge from the andragogic teacher to the student, one student to another in the learning process;

- the use of the principle is based on group forms of learning and allows you to overcome a number of difficulties that arise in heterogeneous groups.

Among the areas implemented in psychological and pedagogical support, we highlight the following as the main ones:

- preventive (implementation of a system of measures to prevent the occurrence of professional problems);

- diagnostic (ensuring the determination of the level of formation of the key competencies of the teacher, its compliance with the normative indicators of the development parameters leading for this stage, as a whole, and for individual key competencies);

- advisory (implementation of special programs for teacher training and their inclusion in the pedagogical process);

- developing (development and implementation of development programs;

- the formation and development of relevant core competencies);

- educational (coverage of innovative approaches in the field of teacher education).

The second block defines the organizational component of the model. Here we attributed:

- participants in the implementation of psychological and pedagogical support (andragogic teacher, teacher, psychologist, teacher-manager);

- specialists in the field of training, management, counseling, social, rehabilitation, correctional and other work among adults;

- forms (individual - individual educational route, counseling; group; collective);

- methods (case-method, method of diagram, modeling, imitation, metaplan, discussion of specific situations, focus groups, point group discussion, etc.);

- tools (adult learning technologies: training, dialectic, positional learning, storytelling, etc.).

The organizational unit is primarily responsible for ensuring the effectiveness of the implementation of the andragogical process (specially organized, positively effective educational process), as well as the integrity and unity of specially organized processes of education, training and development. At the same time, the teacher's interaction with the students is fully ensured in the postgraduate teacher education system, the following role functions of the andragogic teacher are fixed: consultant, supervisor, moderator, facilitator, etc.

The substantive block of the model reflects the mechanisms for the implementation of psychological and pedagogical support, which are implemented through the implementation of various support functions:

1. Individualization of the learning process.

2. Adaptation of the teacher to the learning process in the system of postgraduate teacher education (primary, secondary, subsequent).

3. Providing conditions for increasing the level of professional development of a teacher in the system of postgraduate teacher education.

4. The formation of the key competencies of the teacher as indicators of his professional development: autopsychological, regulatory, reflective, functional.

5. Providing various types of support (low - tutelage, medium - collaborative, above average - consultancy, high - moderator).

The andragogue teacher designs and implements certain support based on the level. The names of the support - “guardian”, “collaborative”, “consulting” and “moderator” - reflect the specific meaning that psychological and pedagogical support takes on depending on the task being solved.

In our opinion, the first three supports are similar to those already existing and described in the scientific literature on pedagogical support (guardian - “protection” and “help”, collaborative - “assistance”, consulting - “interaction”) [6], and the fourth type support - moderator - we allocate independently, as it is possible only in working with adults.

Guardianship support is low. The andragogue teacher provides guardianship support, which consists of the following:

- a real assessment of the level of professional competence;
- the formation of an adequate professional and personal self-esteem;
- formation of the attitude to the need to increase professional knowledge, skills;
- the development by a specialist of new goals for professional life;
- the formation of elementary pedagogical literacy, etc.

Collaborative support is average. The andragogy teacher at this level provides support consisting of the following:

- study and further development of teacher competencies;
- updating of existing professional and social experience;
- making adjustments to the trajectory and pace of professional development;
- acquisition of the personal meaning of professional activity;

Consulting support is above average. The andragogue teacher provides advisory support, which consists of the following:

- coordination of the development goals of the organization and the specialist;
- assisting in overcoming barriers to the development of a specialist;
- the formation and refinement of the criteria for professional and personal growth;
- diagnosis and assessment of the potentials of professional and personal growth;
- assistance in determining the types and forms of advanced training;
- designing a life strategy in accordance with new achievements in the professional field;
- formation of autopsychological competence.

In the process block, the stages of psychological and pedagogical support are considered. It has the following structure:

1. The diagnostic phase, the purpose of which is to identify typical difficulties of teachers in professional activities.

2. The conceptual stage, which generally determines the system of interaction between the andragogue teacher and teachers.

3. The design phase, which is responsible for designing the process of the teacher's learning activities, aimed at improving his key competencies.

4. The formative stage, which occupies an important place in the structure of psychological and pedagogical support, since its main goal is the further formation of key competencies of teachers in the process of studying the proposed program by them.

5. The assessment and corrective phase involves an analysis of the effectiveness of psychological and pedagogical support, the efficiency of programs; assumes current pedagogical diagnostics of the level of formation of key competencies; determination of the reasons and directions for resolving difficulties; designing further pedagogical activities.

6. Reflective stage - teachers' understanding of the experience of collective / individual activities to improve the professional development of teachers in the framework of training in the system of postgraduate teacher education.

The last block (evaluative and effective) contains:

1. The criteria for the effectiveness of psychological and pedagogical support:

- teacher satisfaction with training in the system of postgraduate teacher education;
- the level of formation of the professional formation of the teacher;
- motivation;

- competitiveness (is a professional and personal quality of a teacher, which is acquired and developed in the educational process of vocational training and is expressed in the ability to show their advantages, ensuring demand on the labor market, is an indicator of the quality of the result of professional development of a specialist in the educational process) [4];

- enrichment of the teacher's ideas about professional activity, etc.

2. Levels of professional development of a teacher:

1) Low: the teacher does not have the necessary knowledge, skills and skills, and he is not aware of it.

2) Medium: the teacher realizes that he lacks the necessary knowledge, skills.

3) Above average: the teacher knows what is included in the structure and makes up the content of his professional competencies, can effectively apply them in practice.

4) High: characterized by the fact that there is a complete integration of qualities (professional and personal), i.e., according to A.K. Markova, "professional skills are fully embedded in the behavior of a specialist" [5].

The result of the implementation of psychological and pedagogical support is a higher level of professional development of a teacher, the content of which ensures the success of social and personal self-determination:

- the ability to set goals and make adequate decisions in accordance with individual needs;
- the desire for self-knowledge of their individual characteristics;
- readiness for socially significant activities, overcoming difficulties;
- the ability to establish social and business contacts, etc.

In modern pedagogical research related to the problems of improving pedagogical models, improving the efficiency of the educational process, the emphasis is on identifying, justifying and testing pedagogical conditions that ensure the success of the activities carried out.

For the effective implementation of the model, we have identified the following set of psychological and pedagogical conditions:

1. Creating a supportive educational environment in the system

postgraduate teacher education.

2. Stimulating the independence of teachers in activities to overcome professional difficulties in the system of postgraduate teacher education.

3. The use of various types of psychological and pedagogical support in the system of postgraduate teacher education, depending on the level of professional development of the teacher.

4. The use by a pedagogue-andragogist of a complex of knowledge and skills in the field of andragogy and psychology of an adult (teacher).

5. Informing the teacher about the nature and mechanisms of further professional formation and mastering the ways of this formation.

6. Inclusion of a teacher in multifaceted interactive interaction within the framework of the pedagogical process, activating his professional development.

CONCLUSIONS

Thus, for our work, the importance of using such a research method as modeling in the field of professional development of a teacher is explained by the fact that, firstly, the process of professional development of a teacher is difficult, multi-aspect, difficult to access directly; secondly, this process proceeds under special conditions of training in the system of postgraduate teacher education, it presents a special subject and object of education.

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